

**REFORMS ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF RETAIL INSURANCE
SERVICES IN THE INSURANCE MARKET**

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Abstract

The article presents the state of providing insurance services in the insurance market of our country, reforms in the development of retail insurance services, and suggestions for the development of retail insurance services.

Keywords:

Insurance market, insurance premiums, insurance contracts, insurance compensation, types of retail insurance in the insurance market, retail insurance services.

Insurance services are one of the tools that protect the economy from various financial risks. However, the role of these services in the financial market of our country is not big yet. The share of this industry in the gross domestic product of our country is only 0.4%. For comparison: this figure is 11% in South Korea, 6% in Germany, 1.5% in Russia.

One of the main problems in insurance activity is that insurance services are not attractive enough. For example, 887 billion in the last six months. Some insurance premium was collected, but the amount of insurance coverage paid corresponded to only 11% of the premium. In the world, this indicator is on average 50-60%.

With the independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan, there was a period of fundamental changes in all sectors of the economy. In order to legally ensure the rapid development of the insurance market of the Republic, based on the experience of near and far foreign countries and economically developed countries, the legal documents adopted on the legal development of the insurance sector are giving their results in practice.

The acceleration of the process of modernization of the economy is precisely the increasing attention to the further development of insurance activities, the provision of reliable insurance services to the population of our country, as well as the introduction of innovative methods of providing retail insurance services, the issue of effective use of marketing tools in the provision of retail insurance services is becoming one of the urgent tasks of today.

Also, the insurance sector, like all sectors, is being given great attention and the insurance companies operating in the insurance market have a great

responsibility. The reforms carried out in the insurance market create an important basis for the rapid development of all insurance institutions. Today, 43 insurance companies are operating in the insurance market of Uzbekistan.

Focusing on the analysis, the results of insurance services provided by individual divisions of insurers as of the end of the 9th month of 2022 were summarized. According to studies, 4.5 trillion collected during the reporting period. 2.9 trillion soums of insurance premium. soums or 66.3 percent was contributed by the city of Tashkent. Also, according to the end of the reporting period, the amount of insurance compensation (insurance payment) is 1.9 trillion. amounting to 0.7 trillion soums. soums in general insurance and 1.2 trillion. soums paid to customers in the life insurance industry.

Insurance companies operating in the insurance market provide insurance services to legal entities and individuals. Also, in order to create a competitive environment in the insurance market, effective work is being done to expand retail insurance services in insurance services.

In the new edition of the Law "On Insurance Activities" it is emphasized in the matter of "Protection of the rights and legal interests of consumers of insurance services": consumers of insurance services are free to choose the insurer and insurance services. Insurers are obliged to provide the consumer with the opportunity to familiarize himself with the terms of insurance services at his request.

The insurer shall not force the person to use another insurance service or product of the insurer or any other third party as a condition of using the insurance service or product.

Also, measures to protect the rights of consumers of services provided by professional participants of the insurance market are defined. The authorized state body shall take the following measures in order to fulfill the tasks of protecting the rights of consumers of services provided by professional participants of the insurance market:

- determines the procedure for disclosing information about insurance services provided by insurance organizations;
- identifies systemic deficiencies in the activity of insurance organizations that lead to violations of the rights of consumers of the services they provide, and also takes measures to prevent them;
- applies measures and sanctions against insurance organizations that violate the rights of consumers of their services;

- advises and assists in restoring the violated rights of consumers of services of insurance organizations;
- takes measures to increase the level of financial literacy of the population and business entities.

In order to verify that the professional participants of the insurance market comply with the requirements for their activities in interaction with consumers, the authorized state body has the right to carry out control measures in connection with the purchase of services provided by the professional participants of the insurance market.

In conclusion, the development of retail insurance services in the insurance market is one of the important areas, and the improvement of the mechanism of providing retail insurance services makes an effective contribution to the development of insurance activities.

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